

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM
UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA

DIPARTIMENTO
DI BENI CULTURALI

BIG DATA AND HUMAN EVOLUTION

Making, Using, and Conserving Data

DATE

27-29 OCTOBER 2025, sala conferenze

ROCEEH Group

The Role of Culture in Early
Expansions of Humans
Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and
Humanities

Dr. Miriam Haidle
Dr. Andrew Kandel
Dr. Jesper Pedersen
Dr. Christian Sommer
Dr. Christine Hertler

info: giulia.marciani@unibo.it

BONES LAB – Department of Cultural Heritage (DBC)
and
ROCEEH – The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans
are pleased to organise the workshop
Big Data and Human Evolution: Making, Using, and Conserving Data
27–29 October 2025

This workshop will explore both the theoretical and practical dimensions of creating, using, and preserving large-scale scientific databases in the field of human evolution. Central to the discussion is how digital infrastructures and databases can be effectively developed, utilised, and sustainably maintained, with particular attention to their role in archaeological, paleoanthropological, paleobiological, and paleogeographic research.

Participants will engage with both conceptual frameworks and applied methodologies for data management, focusing on the challenges and opportunities posed by large, interdisciplinary databases. While digital tools are increasingly used across scientific disciplines, critical issues remain regarding data integration, targeted expansion, evaluation, and long-term preservation.

The workshop will also spotlight emerging approaches in data science—such as data mining, machine learning, deep learning, and artificial intelligence—that offer transformative potential for extracting and interpreting complex datasets.

ROCEEH is the research centre responsible for creating the **ROCEEH Out of Africa Database (ROAD)**, the most comprehensive data collection of its kind. ROAD currently contains information on over 2,600 sites, more than 28,000 assemblages, and is based on over 6,300 publications. This geo-relational database integrates knowledge from multiple scientific fields to offer a holistic understanding of the prehistoric world.

During the workshop, participants will be guided in the use of ROAD to address specific research questions posed by the Department of Cultural Heritage, BONES Lab team. Through hands-on data mining, data integration, and collaborative work, the workshop aims to generate new insights and foster connections among researchers.

Workshop Program

Venue: Department of Cultural Heritage (DBC), Aula Conferenze, University of Bologna – Ravenna Campus

Monday, 27 October

Timeslots include discussion ☺ Presentations should be approximately 10–15 minutes

Morning Session – Presentation of the Team and Workshop Aims

- **09:45** – Gathering at Aula Conferenze
- **10:00 – 10:20**
Stefano Benazzi (BONES Lab)
Presentation of BONES Lab, Research Topics, ERC “Last Neanderthal” and other projects
- **10:20 – 11:30**
Tour of BONES Lab Facilities (guided by Stefano Benazzi & BONES Lab staff)
- **11:30 – 12:00** – Coffee Break
- **12:00 – 12:20**
Giulia Marciani (BONES Lab) & Andrew Kandel (ROCEEH)
Workshop Overview and Introduction of ROCEEH Guests. Sharing information, building networks, queries on ROAD, challenges of managing large, complex datasets, integration across sectors, and coordinating large teams
- **12:20 – 12:40**
Andrew Kandel (ROCEEH)
Managing Large Archaeological Datasets: An Overview of the ROAD Database

Discussion

- **13:30 – 14:30** – Lunch

Afternoon Session – Data Management & Integration (Chair: Eugenio Bortolini)

- **14:30 – 15:00**
Gabriele Terlato & Sara Silvestrini (BONES Lab)
Zooarchaeological and ZooMS Datasets for Palaeoecological research
- **15:00 – 15:20**
Christian Sommer (ROCEEH)
Geospatial Datasets, Sustainable Management and Outreach

- **15:20 – 15:40**
Leonardo Vallini (BONES Lab collaborator)
Integrating Genetic and Cultural Data to study Homo sapiens dispersal in Eurasia
 - **15:40 – 16:00**
Jesper Borre Pedersen (ROCEEH)
Neanderthal Demographics: Combining Archaeological and Genetic Evidence
 - **16:00 – 16:40**
Helios Delbrassine (BONES Lab collaborator)
Worldwide patterns in mythology echo the human expansion out of Africa: a case for the joint use of cultural and genetic data
 - ☕ **16:40 – 17:00** – Coffee Break
 - **17:00 – 18:30 – Workshop (Andrew Kandel)**
Introduction to ROAD: Basic Search, Site Summary Sheets, Web GIS
 - ☕ **20.00 Dinner Osteria Passatelli**
-

Tuesday, 28 October

Morning Session – Modelling Data & Case Studies (Chair: Andrew Kandel)

- **09:45** – Gathering at Aula Conferenze
- **10:00 – 10:20**
Christine Hertler (ROCEEH, ERC-LATEUROPE)
Simulating Behavior by Agent-Based Modeling: How Humans May Have Crossed Seamounts (ABM)
- **10:20 – 10:50**
Christine Hertler (ROCEEH, ERC-LATEUROPE)
Cut&Run – an ABM to Determine the Advantage of Tool Behavior
- **10:50 – 11:10**
Giulia Marciani (BONES Lab)
Beyond Labels: Exploring Patterns of Change in Late Pleistocene Human Stone Tool Technology
- **11:10 – 11:30**
Daniel Pereira (BONES Lab)
Modelling Late Pleistocene Technocultural Diversity Using Network Analysis
- ☕ **11:30 – 12:00** – Coffee Break

- **12:00 – 12:20**
Jesper Borre Pedersen (ROCEEH)
Brief Encounters: The Hamburgian Case as a Model for Punctuated Forager Colonisation
- **12:20 – 12:40**
Christian Sommer (ROCEEH)
Prehistoric Landscapes and Human Interaction: Quantitative Approaches Using ROAD

Discussion
- **13:30 – 14:30** – Lunch

Afternoon Session – Data Modelling Workshop

- **14:30 – 16:30 – Workshop (Andrew Kandel & Christian Sommer)**
Querying Data in ROAD Using SQL Tool, Ask ROAD, roadDB (R Package)

Visit to the beautiful Mosaics of Ravenna!

- 20.00 Dinner Ca de Ven

Wednesday, 29 October

Morning Session – Theory and Synthesis (Chair: Giulia Marciani)

- **09:45** – Gathering at Aula Conferenze
- **10:00 – 10:30**
Miriam Haidle (ROCEEH)
Theoretical Framework of ROCEEH: The Model of Evolution and Expansion of Cultural Capacities (EECC) and Beyond
- **10:30 – 11:00**
Eugenio Bortolini (BONES Lab)
Cultural Models in Prehistory
- **11:00 – 11:30**
Miriam Haidle (ROCEEH)
From Micro- to Macroarchaeology with Reverse Engineering
- **11:30 – 12:00** – Coffee Break
- **12:00 – 13:30**
Summary & General Discussion

 13:30 – 14:30 – Lunch

Afternoon Session – Data Modelling Workshop

- **14:30 – 16:30 – Workshop (Andrew Kandel & Christian Sommer)**
Specialised Queries in ROAD: Tailored to Research Needs (in collaboration with BONES Lab participants)